

20IND11 MetHyInfra

Deliverable 8: Technical report on the SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquified hydrogen flow ($Q_{\max} = 5000 \text{ kg/h}$; DN25 - DN50; target uncertainty 0.3 % - 0.8 %) and liquified helium ($Q_{\max} = 4 \text{ kg/h}$; DN4) using master meters (such as Coriolis, ultrasonic and differential pressure devices), calibrated by water and/or by other cryogenic liquids, and recommendations for improving the measurement uncertainty with guidance on the metering deviation of Coriolis meters when using the vapourisation method

DELIVERABLE D8

Lead partner: VSL

Authors: Menne Schakel (VSL), Federica Gugole (VSL), Rémy Maury (Cesame), Daniel Schumann (PTB), Christian Günz (PTB), Hans-Benjamin Böckler (PTB), Oliver Büker (RISE), Jože Kutin (UL), Gregor Bobovnik (UL), Dennis van Putten (DNV)

Confidentiality: Public

Submission date: 31.05.2024

Due date: 30.04.2024

Revision: 1.01

methyinfra.ptb.de

This project "Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows" (MetHyInfra) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Deliverable D8: Technical report on the SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow (Q _{max} = 5000 kg/h; DN25 - DN50; target uncertainty 0.3 % - 0.8 %) and liquified helium (Q _{max} = 4 kg/h; DN4) using master meters (such as Coriolis, ultrasonic and differential pressure devices), calibrated by water and/or by other cryogenic liquids, and recommendations for improving the measurement uncertainty with guidance on the metering deviation of Coriolis meters when using the vaporisation method																															
Funding European Metrology Program for Innovation and Research	Grant agreement 20IND11																														
Project name Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows	Project short name MetHyInfra																														
Author(s) <table border="0"> <tr> <td>Menne Schakel</td> <td>VSL</td> <td>mschakel@vsl.nl</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Federica Gugole</td> <td>VSL</td> <td>fgugole@vsl.nl</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Rémy MAURY</td> <td>CESAME</td> <td>r.mauray@cesame-exadebit.fr</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Daniel Schumann</td> <td>PTB</td> <td>daniel.schumann@ptb.de</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Christian Günz</td> <td>PTB</td> <td>christian.guenz@ptb.de</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hans-Benjamin Böckler</td> <td>PTB</td> <td>hans-benjamin.boeckler@ptb.de</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Oliver Büker</td> <td>RISE</td> <td>oliver.buker@ri.se</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Jože Kutin</td> <td>UL</td> <td>joze.kutin@fs.uni-lj.si</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Gregor Bobovnik</td> <td>UL</td> <td>Gregor.Bobovnik@fs.uni-lj.si</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dennis van Putten</td> <td>DNV</td> <td>Dennis.vanPutten@dnv.com</td> </tr> </table>	Menne Schakel	VSL	mschakel@vsl.nl	Federica Gugole	VSL	fgugole@vsl.nl	Rémy MAURY	CESAME	r.mauray@cesame-exadebit.fr	Daniel Schumann	PTB	daniel.schumann@ptb.de	Christian Günz	PTB	christian.guenz@ptb.de	Hans-Benjamin Böckler	PTB	hans-benjamin.boeckler@ptb.de	Oliver Büker	RISE	oliver.buker@ri.se	Jože Kutin	UL	joze.kutin@fs.uni-lj.si	Gregor Bobovnik	UL	Gregor.Bobovnik@fs.uni-lj.si	Dennis van Putten	DNV	Dennis.vanPutten@dnv.com	Pages 52 pages
Menne Schakel	VSL	mschakel@vsl.nl																													
Federica Gugole	VSL	fgugole@vsl.nl																													
Rémy MAURY	CESAME	r.mauray@cesame-exadebit.fr																													
Daniel Schumann	PTB	daniel.schumann@ptb.de																													
Christian Günz	PTB	christian.guenz@ptb.de																													
Hans-Benjamin Böckler	PTB	hans-benjamin.boeckler@ptb.de																													
Oliver Büker	RISE	oliver.buker@ri.se																													
Jože Kutin	UL	joze.kutin@fs.uni-lj.si																													
Gregor Bobovnik	UL	Gregor.Bobovnik@fs.uni-lj.si																													
Dennis van Putten	DNV	Dennis.vanPutten@dnv.com																													
<p>Summary</p> <p>This report was written as part of activity 4.4.10 from the EMPIR Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows (MetHyInfra) project. The three-year European project commenced on the 1st of June 2021 and focused on providing metrological infrastructure and traceability for high pressure hydrogen flow meter calibration (1000 bar / 3.6 kg/min), fuel cells applications (4 kg/h, 30 bar) and liquid hydrogen. For more details about this project please visit methyinfra.ptb.de.</p>																															
Confidentiality	Public																														

This project (20IND11 MetHyInfra) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

Contents

2	Introduction	6
3	Assessment of alternative fluid calibration to estimate traceable liquefied hydrogen flow measurement uncertainty	7
3.1	Introduction.....	7
3.2	Experimental	9
3.3	Theory.....	12
3.3.1	Analytical CMF models for LH ₂ measurements	12
3.3.2	Uncertainty evaluation	13
3.3.3	Uncertainty budget of density and stiffness model.....	16
3.3.4	On-site calibration uncertainty.....	16
3.4	Results	18
3.5	Discussion and Conclusions.....	21
3.6	Acknowledgements.....	23
3.7	Declaration of competing interest	23
3.8	A Mathematical definition of the raw error	23
4	Measurement corrections for temperature effects in Coriolis mass flow meters for LH ₂ applications 24	
4.1	Temperature correction models.....	25
4.1.1	Correction model A	25
4.1.2	Correction model B	25
4.1.3	Correction model C	26
4.1.4	Correction model D	26
4.2	Results.....	27
5	PTB vaporisation method report	29
5.1	Introduction.....	29
5.2	Experimental Setup	29
5.2.1	Meter under Test	29
5.2.2	Vaporisation test rig.....	31
5.3	Conducted Experiments	32
5.3.1	MUT calibrations	32
5.3.2	Laminar-Flow-Elements.....	37
5.3.3	Cryogenic experiments.....	39
5.4	Summary and Conclusion	43

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

5.5	Acknowledgements	44
6	Cryogenic LDV primary standard: modification for LH ₂	45
7	Summary	47
7.1	SI-traceable LH ₂ flow measurement uncertainty	47
7.2	Recommendations to improve LH ₂ flow measurement uncertainty.....	48
7.3	Guidance on Coriolis meter deviations when using the vaporisation method	49
	References	50

2. Introduction

This deliverable summarizes the experimental work performed within the MetHyInfra project on establishing SI-traceability for liquefied hydrogen (LH₂) flows. Two ranges were covered:

1. Industrial flow rates (1000 - 5000 kg/h and pressure up to 10 bar(a); DN25 – DN 50)
2. Laboratory flow rates (up to 4 kg/h and pressures up to 1.5 bar(a); DN3)

Traceability of liquefied hydrogen flow measurements was developed by a three-pronged approach: (I) assessment of the transferability of water and LNG calibrations to LH₂ conditions; (II) cryogenic Laser Doppler Velocimetry (LDV) adapted to LH₂ flow applications; (III) assessment of the transferability of water, liquid nitrogen, and liquid helium calibrations in the vaporisation method to LH₂ conditions. The first method covers industrial flow rates (see point 1 above) and is detailed in Chapter 3. The second method covers industrial flow rates (see point 1 above) and is detailed in Chapter 6. The third method covers the laboratory flow rates (see point 2 above) and is detailed in Chapter 5. Assessment of the transferability of alternative fluid calibrations to low temperature flows requires modelling of temperature effects that influence flow meter measurement. A Coriolis flow meter model is developed in Chapter 3. The errors of the analytical temperature correction models for Coriolis flow meters, which were determined using a numerical finite element (FE) reference model, are presented in Chapter 4.

In Chapter 7 a summary is provided as inferred from Chapters 3 - 6 covering:

- SI-traceable LH₂ flow measurement uncertainty
- Recommendations for improving LH₂ flow measurement uncertainty
- Deviations of Coriolis meters when using the vaporisation method

3 Assessment of alternative fluid calibration to estimate traceable liquified hydrogen flow measurement uncertainty¹

Federica Gugole¹, Menne D. Schakel¹, Maarten Brugman², and Aleksandr Druzhkov²

¹VSL B.V., Thijsseweg 11, 2629 JA Delft, the Netherlands

²Emerson Automation Solutions, Ede, The Netherlands

March 30, 2024

Abstract

The usage of liquefied hydrogen (LH2) is growing fast as the EU aims to be climate-neutral by 2050. Therefore, reliable and consistent measurements of LH2 amounts will become increasingly important for custody transfers. Flow meters are customarily employed to determine the amount transferred when transporting resources from a seller to a buyer. Reliability and consistency of flow meter measurements is established from calibration, which is typically performed in dedicated calibration laboratories accredited to the ISO/IEC 17025 standard. Due to the lack of facilities being able to calibrate LH2 flow meters directly with LH2 as calibration fluid, the question arises whether the measurement error of the calibration performed on a different fluid and different process conditions are representative for the errors when measuring LH2. An on-site calibration of two turbine meters measuring LH2 flow was performed. A Coriolis mass flow meter calibrated on water was used as a reference in conjunction with a dedicated flow meter model, which was validated by a directly SI-traceable calibration on liquefied natural gas. LH2 flow rates were within 1000 kg/h and 3000 kg/h, which are directly relevant to hydrogen transport by LH2 trailers. The analysis of the measurement data reveal errors on totalized mass ranging from 2.0 % to 2.9 % with a total calibration uncertainty of 1.3 % ($k = 2$), where the main uncertainty source was identified as the on-site density estimate necessary to convert the volume flow measurements into mass flow measurements. The calibration uncertainty is likely to be lower when comparing meters both measuring mass (or volume) flow rate. The results indicate the need for reliable and accurate temperature measurements (the latter allowing for an accurate density estimate), so that volume based and mass-based amount measurements in custody transfer LH2 processes can be compared with smaller uncertainties.

Keywords: liquefied hydrogen, measurement uncertainty, SI-traceability, climate-neutral economy, Euro- pean Green Deal

3.1 Introduction

The EU aims to be climate-neutral by 2050 – an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. This objective is at the heart of the European Green Deal [1] and in line with the EU’s commitment to global climate action under the Paris Agreement (COP21). The hydrogen strategy for a climate neutral Europe [2] identifies liquefied hydrogen (LH2) as a means of energy transport to reach the Green Deal objective. The usage of LH2 is thus growing fast, and transportation sectors are

¹ Chapter 3 was submitted to the International Journal of Hydrogen Energy [34] and is available as a [preprint](#). Minor typesetting and/or textual changes apply.

pushing towards this solution (aircraft, liquefied hydrogen carriers, trains). In a similar fashion to trading natural gas or oil, the widespread use of LH₂ will need to be supported by reliable and consistent measurements to determine amounts of LH₂ traded during custody transfer. Flow meters are customarily employed during the custody transfer process to determine the amount transferred when transporting resources from a seller to a buyer. Reliability and consistency of flow meter measurements is established from calibration of flow meters, which inherently entails the establishment of a direct link with the SI-units. The calibration is typically performed in dedicated laboratories accredited to the ISO/IEC 17025 documentary standard [3]. Given the physical working principle of a flow meter (e.g., based on the Coriolis effect or based on ultrasound) the measurement error of that flow meter may be influenced by the physical properties of the fluid flowing through it and its specific process conditions (e.g., temperature of the atmosphere surrounding the pipe in which the flow meter is installed). de Jonge et al. [4] show results on flow rate measurements at liquefied helium conditions (-269 °C) indicating flow rate errors of about 1 % for flow rates up to 0.03 kg/s (18 kg/h). Due to the lack of LH₂ calibration facilities with industrial flow rates (up to 5000 kg/h), a question arises on the degree to which the measurement error of the calibration likely performed on water at ambient conditions is representative for its error when measuring LH₂ at very low temperatures (-253 °C at atmospheric pressure). For liquefied natural gas (LNG) it is known that the flow meter error on water, as established during the water flow calibration in an ISO/IEC 17025 accredited laboratory, is not necessarily exactly the same as when using it with LNG [5], [6]. This is relevant for LH₂, since (1) both LNG and LH₂ are cryogenic fluids, and (2) the physical working principle of the flow meters are coinciding (e.g., Coriolis or ultrasonic). Therefore, the additional measurement uncertainty of a water calibrated LH₂ flow meter in a LH₂ flow measuring environment must be (quantitatively) investigated as this will determine the achievable accuracy during the custody transfer.

In this paper, Coriolis mass flow meter (CMF) models will be employed and combined with direct SI-traceable calibrations on water and LNG of a single CMF to quantitatively estimate the achievable, (indirect) SI-traceable flow measurement uncertainty of LH₂ CMFs. LH₂ flow experimental results will be presented in which the calibrated CMF, with its base uncertainty, was used as a reference in the calibration of turbine meters along the same flow line. Inherent to the calibration another (larger) uncertainty of the LH₂ turbine meter error is presented.

A literature survey was performed into the (publicly available) analytical models for CMF [7]. Two analytical models were found, one for a straight tube [8] and one for a U-shape CMF [9]. Combining the results of a CMF calibration on water and the available analytical models of [7] and [8], Wu et al. [10] and Wu and Kenbar [11] estimated an uncertainty budget for LNG measurements of 0.20 % (coverage factor $k = 2$) and 0.24 % ($k = 2$) for a straight tube and for a U-shape CMF, respectively. To the best knowledge of the authors, no similar work has been done for LH₂ measurements aside from the recently published patent [12], which is applicable to generic CMF's shapes and thus to our case study where a delta-shape CMF was used to take the measurements, for which no analytical model was found in the literature. Therefore, here two analytical meter models applicable to CMF's measurements from [12] are employed to propagate the uncertainties of the quantities that appear in the analytical equation using the Monte Carlo method according to the Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement - Supplement 1

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

[13]. Each of the influencing variables is carefully analysed to provide the best available quantitative information of its uncertainty.

The results presented are directly relevant to a LH₂ trailer (un)loading in transport applications as the flow rates considered are ranging from 1000 kg/h to 3000 kg/h.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 0 provides information about the experimental setup. Section 3.3 lists in detail how each uncertainty component has been estimated and thus contributes to the final uncertainty budget. The findings and subsequent discussion and conclusions are detailed in sections 0 and 0 respectively.

3.2 Experimental

A commercially available CMF100 (nominal flow rate on water at about 16,000 kg/h) CMF (manufacturer Emerson) suitable for the measurement of LH₂ was tested with water in Emerson's ISO/IEC 17025 accredited calibration laboratory and with LNG in VSL's SI-traceable calibration facility. This provided the flow meter with SI-traceability directly to mass flow units with so-called alternative fluids (i.e., fluids different from LH₂, like water and LNG). Figure 3-1 shows calibration results of a CMF100. For this flow meter, the error on water is at around 0.0 % of reference mass flow rate, while it is at about -0.25 % on LNG. During the LNG calibration, the meter was insulated and the temperatures ranged from -171 °C to -166 °C.

The setup of the LH₂ flow experiments is depicted in Figure 3-2. LH₂ flow is created from setting a driving pressure in the gas phase of the storage tank. Two turbine meters (approximate maximum flow rate at 45000 kg/h) are combined with their pressure and temperature measurements into a reference mass flow rate using a computed LH₂ density (assuming 100 % parahydrogen) for the conversion of volume flow rate to mass flow rate. These two turbine meters are calibrated on water on an annual basis. The calibrated CMF was installed at the connecting flange of the test bench (Figure 3-3). A flexible hose was used to guide the LH₂ to the stack where the hydrogen was then flared. An orifice was installed to ensure sufficient pressure for the hydrogen to remain in liquefied state. The CMF and return line were carefully insulated with Armaflex, which was wrapped tightly around the piping. The zero was set at ambient conditions and it was ensured that with a cooled down line the zero specification at 0.47 kg/h was met.

The overview of measurement batches is displayed in Table 3-2. A single measurement batch was run per flow point, and this sequence was followed sequentially. A typical calibration procedure is to take several measurement batches per nominal flow point (starting at the highest flow), after which the second-to-highest flow is set to again take several repeats. The unconventional order as displayed in the Table 3-2 was chosen to (1) be able to adjust the test protocol in case of issues during the measurements without running out of stored LH₂ and (2) to potentially investigate if the order itself affects the measurement error (c.f., repeats 10 - 15). The lowest flow point at around 1180 kg/h is relatively high with respect to the minimal flow rate at which the CMF100 (at about 400 kg/h) fulfils manufacturers specifications at ambient conditions. The reason is that sufficient flow is required in order to avoid boil-off of LH₂ during the batch. Avoidance of boil-off could not be ensured at flow rates below 1150 kg/h. Boil-off of LH₂ would create a gas/liquid mixture at which point the quality of the measurements could not be ensured. It was made sure

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

that the drive-gain of the CMF100 remained sufficiently low to indicate the absence of significant boil-off. Prior to the measurement batches, a small batch (few seconds) LH₂ flow higher than the set point was created just before the batch to ensure the avoidance of Thermal Acoustic Oscillations (TAO) [14] created within the appendages of the Figure 3-2 flow line. For repeat number 4 this was not performed, and it was shown to create TAO's manifesting as strong flow oscillations. Lastly, we remark that the measurements of the turbine meter have been collected using the data acquisition system of the facility, which recorded a data point on average every 0.001 s, while the measurements of the CMF have been recorded with the data acquisition system of the CMF itself, which recorded every 0.05 s on average. Therefore, an additional uncertainty source due to the difference in the recording frequency should be considered in the uncertainty analysis.

Calibration fluid	Reference flow kg/s	Error %	Expanded uncertainty U %
Water	0.51	0.019	0.017
Water	0.76	0.017	0.017
Water	1.03	0.016	0.017
Water	1.28	0.017	0.017
Water	1.54	0.015	0.017
Water	1.81	0.016	0.017
Water	2.06	0.008	0.017
Water	3.90	0.006	0.017
LNG	2.016	-0.26	0.18
LNG	1.674	-0.26	0.18
LNG	1.246	-0.25	0.18
LNG	0.831	-0.23	0.18
LNG	0.497	-0.23	0.31
LNG	0.624	-0.25	0.31

Table 3-1: LH₂ CMF100 calibration results using water and LNG as alternative calibration fluids.

Figure 3-1: LH₂ CMF100 calibration results using water and LNG as alternative calibration fluids. Water calibration results are obtained from Emerson's ISO/IEC 17025 accredited calibration laboratory. LNG results are obtained in VSL's SI-traceable calibration facility. Calibration uncertainty is indicated by the error (uncertainty, $k = 2$) bars (water uncertainty is small with respect to the symbol size). The manufacturer's specification is obtained from [15] and includes the zero specification at 0.47 kg/h.

Figure 3-2: Schematic of LH₂ experiments at the Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR).

Figure 3-3: Picture of the CMF100 (1) as installed during LH₂ flow tests. Also displayed are: flow direction (arrows), pressure measurement port (2), temperature measurement position (3), flexible hose (4), (location of) orifice (5).

Table 3-2: Overview of measurement batches. Run time reported is as recorded by the CMF data acquisition system. Repeat #4 is crossed out as TAOs created unsteady flow conditions.

Repeat #	Flow rate		run time s
	kg/s	kg/h	
1	0.769	2769	29.407
2	0.494	1777	43.107
3	0.326	1172	84.949
4	0.772	2780	33.838
5	0.498	1791	63.250
6	0.331	1193	93.479
7	0.766	2759	34.569
8	0.491	1766	64.801
9	0.329	1184	91.952
10	0.766	2756	32.814
11	0.491	1767	48.241
12	0.329	1184	104.162
13	0.329	1185	91.567
14	0.494	1779	61.593
15	0.770	2771	34.407

3.3 Theory

3.3.1 Analytical CMF models for LH₂ measurements

The relationship between mass flow rate and the flow measurement of a CMF is dependent on the temperature of the fluid being measured. A linear temperature compensation was developed to compensate for varying temperature conditions, but when CMF were first applied to cryogenic applications, it was noticed that at extremely low temperatures the elastic properties of the steel behave non-linearly [16] and this in turn affects the tube's stiffness. Thus, a correction was developed for cryogenic applications down to -233 °C

$$\dot{m} = FCF(\Delta t - \Delta t_0)(\phi_0 + \phi_1\Delta T + \phi_2\Delta T^2 + \phi_3\Delta T^3 + \phi_4\Delta T^4) \quad (1)$$

where \dot{m} is the mass flow rate, FCF is the flow calibration factor, Δt is the fundamental Coriolis time measurement, Δt_0 is the Δt value at no-flow conditions, ΔT is the temperature difference in °C with respect to 0 °C, and ϕ_0, \dots, ϕ_4 are polynomial coefficients that characterize the nonlinear Young's modulus behaviour.

Temperature has an important effect also on the geometry of the meter itself. As the temperature increases (decreases), the steel expands (shrinks) thus modifying the geometric parameters of the meter. Therefore, an additional correction term is added to equation as follows

$$\dot{m} = FCF(\Delta t - \Delta t_0)(\phi_0 + \phi_1\Delta T + \phi_2\Delta T^2 + \phi_3\Delta T^3 + \phi_4\Delta T^4)(1 + \alpha\Delta T) \quad (2)$$

where α is the thermal expansion coefficient.

Recently a method to compensate the mass flow measurement of CMFs using the fluid density and the drive frequency instead of the Young's modulus has been patented [12]. According to this method, the mass flow rate is calculated as

$$\dot{m} = FCF(\Delta t - \Delta t_0) \frac{\rho_f(1+\alpha\Delta T)^3 + C_2}{K^2 C_1} \quad (3)$$

where ρ_f is the density of the fluid being measured, K is the tube period, and

$$C_1 = \frac{D_2 - D_1}{K_2^2 - K_1^2}; C_2 = K_1^2 \frac{D_2 - D_1}{K_2^2 - K_1^2}$$

are calibration constants, where D_1 and D_2 are the density values of air and of water, respectively, and K_1 and K_2 are the frequency values measured by the CMF when measuring air or water, respectively.

In the remainder of this paper, we will refer to equation (2) as the *stiffness correction model* and to equation (3) as the *density correction model*. In the next section we evaluate the standard uncertainty associated to equations (2) and (3) for LH₂ measurements.

3.3.2 Uncertainty evaluation

In order to estimate the standard uncertainty associated to the stiffness and to the density correction model, we combine the contribution of several uncertainty sources. Uncertainty sources that apply to both models are: repeatability, zero stability, pressure and temperature effects, timing (i.e., Δt), calibration constants and thermal expansion. Specific to the density correction model there are additional uncertainties associated to density and to the tube period, while the stiffness correction model has an additional uncertainty source given by the Young's modulus. In what follows, we describe how each uncertainty source has been treated and estimated.

3.3.2.1 Repeatability

CMF's repeatability uncertainty for water measurements is included in the total calibration uncertainty and thus already included in the uncertainty associated to the FCF, see paragraph 3.3.2.6.

3.3.2.2 Zero stability

According to the manufacturer specifications, the zero specification (z.s.) of a CMF100 is 0.47 kg/h [15].

We treat this number as the half-width of a uniform distribution and compute the percent error with respect to the lowest flow rate measured during the test (0.33 kg/s) as a worst-case scenario estimate. In fact, looking at the formula for percent error at the flow rate of interest, i.e.,

$$e_{zero} = \frac{z.S.}{\dot{m}} \cdot 100 \%,$$

it is evident that the highest relative error due to zero stability is obtained at the lowest flow rate. Thus the standard uncertainty due to zero stability is $u_{zero} \approx 0.02 \%$ at $\dot{m} = 0.33 \text{ kg/s}$.

3.3.2.3 Pressure

It is well known that larger flow meters have a pressure dependency [17] and recent studies found that the effect due to pressure is in general agreement with the manufacturer's specification [9], [18]. During the LH₂ measurements, the CMF software automatically applied a pressure correction based on a pre-set pressure for each setpoint. Therefore, the pressure uncertainty contribution is due to differences between the pressure measured by the pressure sensor of the facility in correspondence of the CMF and the pressure set in CMF software. We estimate the expanded uncertainty due to the pressure correction as $U_p = |c_p(\text{measured pressure} - \text{set pressure})|$ where $c_p = -0.003 \%/bar$ is the pressure correction factor. The standard uncertainty contribution $u_p = U_p/2$ varies slightly between repeats, and it has been estimated to be approximately 0.0009 % in the worst case. We remark that in this derivation the pressure measurement uncertainty, the pressure drop across the CMF, and the uncertainty in the pressure correction factor specified by the manufacturer are assumed negligible.

3.3.2.4 Temperature

Temperature is arguably the most important uncertainty source since it affects other quantities such as density, Young's modulus and thermal expansion, and is also present by itself in both correction model equations. VSL's LNG facility calibration data show a maximum error of 3 K in the temperature readings of insulated CMF meters. As the temperature difference between ambient temperature around the pipe and cryogenic flow temperature within the pipe increases, errors in the temperature measurement are expected to increase. Therefore, we considered a maximum error of 5 K (half-width of a uniform distribution) for the temperature measurements at LH₂ operating conditions, which coincides with the statement in the patent [12]. Such assumption corresponds to a standard uncertainty $u_t = 5/\sqrt{3} \approx 2.89 \text{ K}$ for the temperature measurements of an insulated CMF.

3.3.2.5 Timing

The CMF has a time resolution in the order of picoseconds and its timing uncertainty is considered to be negligible.

3.3.2.6 Calibration constants

One calibration constant that appears in both correction methods is the FCF. The uncertainty associated with the FCF is given by the total calibration uncertainty from the water calibration. Thus, for this application we $u_{FCF} = 0.017/2 \approx 0.009 \%$.

The density correction model has two additional calibration constants $C_1 = (D_2 - D_1)/(K_2^2 - K_1^2)$ and $C_2 = K_1^2(D_2 - D_1)/(K_2^2 - K_1^2)$. The uncertainty in D_1 (D_2) is given by the accuracy in measuring the density of air (water), which has been estimated as 0.09 kg/m³ (0.08 kg/m³) and are treated as standard uncertainty of a normal distribution. A linear extrapolation is then performed to the nominal values $D_1 = 0 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $D_2 = 1 \text{ g/cm}^3$ for easiness of presentation. Since the air (water) density is (very) close to the nominal value 0 (1), we consider the extrapolation uncertainty to be negligible. We consider negligible also

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

the uncertainty in K_1 and K_2 since their estimation is based on time measurements which are significantly more accurate than the density measurements. When propagating the uncertainty in D_1 and D_2 we get an uncertainty of 0.012 % for C_1 and C_2 .

3.3.2.7 Thermal expansion

The thermal expansion of the material of the flow meter is usually modelled as a percentage linear expansion which, for stainless steel 316 in the temperature range 4-293 K, is given by [19]. At $T = 20$ K the mean value of the thermal expansion coefficient α is 0.99696 [19] with an associated expanded uncertainty $U_\alpha = 0.015$ %. Thus, the standard uncertainty is $u_\alpha \approx 0.008$ %, assuming a normal distribution. For more details see [7].

3.3.2.8 Density

In [12] it is mentioned that ideally the density should be estimated using an equation of state (EOS) that takes as input temperature, pressure and composition. Therefore we use the publicly available software TREND 5.0 [20] to estimate the density of the fluid given temperature, pressure and composition. In particular, we use the EOS from [21] to estimate the density of pure hydrogen, where we assume that it is 100 % parahydrogen. We estimated the uncertainties in the density due to uncertainties in the input values using the numerical approximation described in the Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement [22], where we assume that the uncertainties in temperature, pressure and composition are mutually independent. We then combine the so-obtained uncertainty with the uncertainty of the EOS itself.

Also, in this case we considered a maximum error of 5 K (half-width of a uniform distribution) for the temperature sensors, which correspond to a standard uncertainty $u_t = 5/\sqrt{3} \approx 2.89$ K for the temperature measurements. The temperature uncertainty results into a density uncertainty due to temperature $u_{\rho,T} \approx 3.65$ kg/m³ (note that the sensitivity coefficient is included in the estimated number). Regarding the pressure measurement results we considered a standard uncertainty of 1 %. The maximum density uncertainty resulting from the pressure uncertainty has been estimated as $u_{\rho,p} \approx 0.02$ kg/m³. To estimate the effect of impurities on the density of the fluid at given temperature and pressure, we compared the density estimate for pure liquefied hydrogen to the density estimate of liquefied hydrogen including the maximum level of impurities specified in the composition certificate from the supplier. In this calculation we had to consider normal hydrogen (instead of parahydrogen) because at the time of writing TREND 5.0 could not compute a mixture of parahydrogen and other chemical components different from hydrogen. The difference due to the presence of impurities was four orders of magnitudes smaller than the uncertainty due to temperature changes. Thus, we decided to neglect this uncertainty source. Lastly, [21] reports an EOS uncertainty in density of 0.1 % at temperatures from the triple point to 250 K and at pressures up to 40 MPa. We thus set $u_{\rho,EOS} = 0.1$ %. Combining these uncertainties according to the law of propagation of uncertainty gives the standard uncertainty for density $u_\rho \approx 3.65$ kg/m³, which we treat as the standard deviation of a normal distribution.

3.3.2.9 Tube period

The measurement of the CMF's tube period is carefully calibrated during the manufacturing process and the meter itself has been manufactured specifically for the measurement of cryogenic fluids. We propagate the tube period deviation reported in [12] through the model equation (3), where we use the average value of the tube period during measurements instead

of its nominal value. We consider this deviation as the standard deviation of a normal distribution.

3.3.2.10 Young's modulus

To the knowledge of the authors, [16] provides the only publicly available measurement data of the Young's modulus of stainless steel 316 (the material of the CMF used during the measurements). Their associated uncertainty is reported in [23] as $u_E = 1.9 \%$. Little information is given about how the uncertainty budget has been obtained or whether it is a standard or expanded uncertainty budget. A somewhat more detailed uncertainty budget has been provided in [24] for stainless steel 304. Assuming that the uncertainty budget for stainless steel 316 has been obtained in a similar fashion as the one for stainless steel 304, we would then have to consider only the repeatability component since the steel material lot-to-lot variability is calibrated out during the calibration at ambient temperature. This assumption allows us to reduce the uncertainty associated to the Young's modulus to $u_E = 0.5 \%$, which we will consider as a standard uncertainty. For more details see [7].

3.3.3 Uncertainty budget of density and stiffness model

To obtain an uncertainty budget of the density (3) and of the stiffness correction model (2), we propagate the uncertainties of the quantities that appear in the equation using the Monte Carlo method [13]. We then add the uncertainty contributions due to zero stability and pressure to the result of the Monte Carlo evaluation using the law of propagation of uncertainties [22]. Following this procedure we obtained a standard uncertainty $u_{p,corr} = 0.18 \%$ and $u_{E,corr} = 0.51 \%$ for the density and the stiffness correction model respectively, where the dominant uncertainty sources are the density estimate and the uncertainty associated with the measurement of the Young's modulus.

Table 3-3: Uncertainty components of the total standard uncertainty budget of the stiffness and of the density correction models at liquefied hydrogen temperature. NA = Not Applicable. MC = Uncertainty propagated through the model equation using the Monte Carlo method [13].

Uncertainty component	Estimation source	Probability distribution	Standard uncertainty contribution (%)	
			Stiffness	Density
CMF repeatability	Included in FCF uncertainty	NA	NA	NA
CMF zero stability	Manufacturer specification	uniform	0.02	0.02
Pressure effect	Calibration data and manufacturer specification	normal	0.0009	0.0009
Temperature	Proxy from LNG facility	uniform	MC	MC
Timing	Considered negligible	NA	NA	NA
Calibration constants	Calibration data and manufacturer specification	normal	MC	MC
Thermal expansion coefficient	Literature	normal	MC	MC
Density	Propagation through EOS	normal	NA	MC
Tube period	Manufacturer specification	normal	NA	MC
Young's modulus	Literature	normal	0.5	NA

3.3.4 On-site calibration uncertainty

When installing the CMF in the LH₂ flow facility to provide traceability to the SI-units, it is used a so-called transfer standard. On-site LH₂ total calibration uncertainty is now a function of the total calibration uncertainty of the transfer standard and on-site uncertainty sources. For instance, temperature and pressure sensors will create additional uncertainties, and using a calibrated transfer standard in an on-site facility will bring in new sources of

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

repeatability uncertainty. Using the measurement data we estimated a repeatability standard uncertainty of 0.07 % (more details in section 0).

Since in the LH₂ measurements we are comparing meters based on different principles (volume flow rate measurements in case of the turbine meters and mass flow rate measurements in case of the CMF), we consider an additional uncertainty source due to the density estimate done by the facility. The reported uncertainty of the pressure and temperature sensors at the on-site facility are about 1 % of the maximum operating pressure (16 bar) and temperature (40 K), respectively. When analysing the data, a 0.15 K discrepancy in the zero setting of the CMF's and of the facility's temperature sensors was found. Thus, the temperature uncertainty of the facility's sensors becomes 0.4 + 0.15 = 0.55 K, which we treat as the half-width of a uniform distribution. We note that accurate temperature measurements of cryogenic fluids are challenging and a well-known issue in the literature [25], [26], thus they could have large associated errors and uncertainties. We then propagate these uncertainties through the EOS to obtain (after considering also the uncertainty of the EOS) an estimate of the additional uncertainty in the density estimate, where we assumed 100 % parahydrogen as in 3.3.2.8. The stated temperature and pressure uncertainties resulted into an additional standard uncertainty of 0.57 % in the flow rate measurement due to the on-site density uncertainty.

Other important potential uncertainty sources are so-called line pack effects and synchronization timing uncertainty. Line pack effects arise from density changes in the interconnected volume during a flow measurement batch, which we calculate as described in [27]. The line pack effect was estimated to be lower than 0.02 % of mass flow rate for most runs except for repeat #4 for which it was estimated as circa 0.10 %. This relatively large effect is due to the presence of TAO's during the measurements in repeat #4. Therefore, we exclude the measurements of run #4 from the analysis.

Since the measurements have been recorded using two different data acquisition systems (i.e., the one of the facility for the turbine meters and the CMF's system for its own measurements), two additional uncertainty contributions have to be considered due to the synchronization timing uncertainty. The first one is due to a potential delay in the CMF's system when receiving the synchronization signal emitted by the facility equipment. Since the data acquisition system of the facility recorded the data using a countdown as time stamp (without recording the clock time of the first measurement), it was not straightforward to estimate the delay when receiving the synchronization signal. However, a conservative estimate of 2 s has been obtained using the available data. Considering the physics of the flow, the uncertainty contribution of this delay is supposed to be larger if the flow rate undergoes relatively large changes from unstable flow conditions during this time. We therefore estimate the uncertainty contribution due to the delay as

$$\frac{\text{delay}}{\text{batch time}} \frac{\text{std}(\text{flow rate})}{\text{avg}(\text{flow rate})}$$

where we use the within run standard deviation of the flow rate as an indicator of the amplitude of the changes undergone by the flow rate. The value of this uncertainty source varies among the runs and it is about 0.01 %. We treat this estimate as the standard deviation of a normal distribution. The second uncertainty contribution due to the synchronization timing is caused by the different recording frequencies of the two systems. We estimate such uncertainty component as

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

$$\frac{|sampling\ interval\ CMF - sampling\ interval\ turbine|_{avg}(flow\ rate)}{total\ mass}$$

which we consider as the half-width of a uniform distribution. Its value ranges between 0.03 % and 0.09 % with higher values at higher flow rates.

Lastly, when calculating the deviations of the meter under test, the reference meter is usually corrected for its known deviations in the measurements at process conditions. However, by lack of a SI-traceable calibration directly on LH₂, in this case it is not possible to know the deviation of the transfer standard at LH₂ conditions with sufficient corroboration. Therefore, by extrapolating from the known errors determined from direct calibration on LNG and recognizing it to fall within the uncertainties predicted from (2), and (3), we estimate an error of 0.4 % at LH₂ conditions which we treat as the half-width of a uniform distribution. We then combine it with the other uncertainty sources using the law of propagation of uncertainty [22]. From the above, we obtained a base uncertainty of the reference standard for the on-site calibration at LH₂ process conditions of 0.65 % ($k = 1$) for the raw errors based on totalized mass.

Table 3-4: Uncertainty components of the total standard uncertainty budget of the on-site calibration uncertainty.

Uncertainty component	Probability distribution	Standard uncertainty contribution (%)
Density model uncertainty	normal	0.18
Repeatability	normal	0.07
On-site density uncertainty	normal	0.57
Delay in synchronization signal	normal	0.01
Different recording frequency	normal	0.09
Deviations at process conditions	uniform	$0.40/\sqrt{3}$
Total on-site standard uncertainty	normal	0.65

3.4 Results

Looking at the mass flow measurements during a batch (Figure 3-4), it is possible to notice that the stiffness correction model yields consistently higher flow rate values with respect to the density correction model. We note that in this application, the stiffness correction model was used beyond its range since it is being applied to measurements that were executed at temperature lower than -233 °C. Therefore, the approximation used to account for the Young's modulus effect might not be as accurate at temperatures below the stated range of validity of the model. The difference in the measurement results is about 0.73 % for each repeat with an associated standard uncertainty of 0.55 % ($k = 1$), see Figure 3-5. The uncertainty has been estimated by propagation of the uncertainties of the density and of the stiffness correction model via the Monte Carlo method [13] through the raw error equation (see Appendix A). The 95 % confidence interval of the difference between the two correction models contains zero, thus the difference between the two correction models is not statistically significant and the measurement results obtained with the two models can be said to be in agreement.

When comparing the combined measurements of the turbine meters with the CMF measurements, errors between 2.0 % and 2.9 % with associated standard uncertainty of about 0.67 % ($k = 1$) have been observed in the totalized mass, see Table 3-5. These results have been obtained by propagating the on-site calibration uncertainty via the Monte Carlo method through the raw error equation. Thus, the turbine meter is significantly overestimating

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

the mass flow rate. The mean raw error on the totalized mass is 2.22 %, 2.60 % and 2.66 % with estimated repeatability uncertainty of 0.071 %, 0.063 % and 0.096 % for setpoints 0.35 kg/s, 0.50 kg/s and 0.80 kg/s, respectively. We approximate the repeatability uncertainty as $u_{repeat} = 0.07 \%$. Lastly, we note that the errors show a dependency on the flow rate, where lower deviations are recorded at the lower flow rates, see Figure 3-6.

Figure 3-4: Example of the mass flow measurements during one of the batches. The red line displays the measurements as calculated using the stiffness method (2), while the blue line has been obtained using the density correction method (3). It can be noted that the density corrected measurements are systematically smaller than the values obtained using the correction based on the Young's modulus.

Figure 3-5: Relative error between the CMF measurements corrected using equation (2) and the measurements corrected using equation (3). The results obtained with equation (3) have been considered as reference. The error bars denote the 95% confidence interval ($k = 2$).

Table 3-5: Overview of relative errors where the density model is considered as reference.

Repeat #	Stiffness vs Density %	Turbine vs CMF %
1	0.71	2.45
2	0.73	2.72
3	0.74	2.45
4	0.70	1.96
5	0.72	2.44
6	0.73	2.03
7	0.70	2.58
8	0.72	2.63
9	0.73	2.20
10	0.70	2.82
11	0.72	2.45
12	0.75	2.13
13	0.79	2.28
14	0.78	2.73
15	0.75	2.85

Figure 3-6: Relative error in totalized mass between the CMF measurements corrected using equation (2) and the measurements of the turbine meters. The CMF's measurements have been considered as reference. The error bars denote the 95% confidence interval ($k = 2$).

3.5 Discussion and Conclusions

The results show that the two correction methods for CMF measurements agree to each other within the stated uncertainty (even though the stiffness model was applied beyond its stated validity range). However, it is worth noting that the stiffness correction method has a larger uncertainty (most of which is due to the uncertainty in the measurements of the Young's modulus) and consistently estimates a higher value with respect to the values obtained with the density correction method. More accurate measurements of the Young's modulus (and, potentially, a more accurate approximation of the Young's modulus at temperatures below $-233\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) would help to reduce the uncertainty of the stiffness correction method, and it could possibly reduce the difference between the measurement values obtained with the two correction methods. In any case, in order to obtain full direct traceability and to establish which of the two correction models is closer to the true value, a dedicated LH_2 flow standard with direct traceability to SI-units is necessary.

In a similar fashion as described in section 3.3, it is possible to derive an uncertainty budget of the density correction method when applied to LNG measurements. We note that many of the uncertainty components remain the same as some uncertainty contributions seen during LNG calibration have been used as proxy for LH_2 measurements. The uncertainty components that should be modified are the zero stability (the minimum flow tested during the LNG calibration was 0.497 kg/s), the uncertainty due to the pressure correction (during the LNG measurements there was no set pressure, thus the uncertainty in the correction is due to the uncertainty of the pressure measurement and of the pressure correction factor), the uncertainty in the temperature measurement (in this case we consider a uniform distribution with half-width of 3 K), and the uncertainty in the density estimate. To estimate the uncertainty contribution due to density, we propagate temperature and SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

pressure uncertainty through the GERG-2008 EOS [28] instead of the equation of state by [21], since the latter is valid only for hydrogen and the former is indicated in ISO 20765 part 2 [29] as a suitable equation of state for the calculation of the thermodynamic properties of natural gas. The so estimated standard uncertainty of the density correction model for LNG measurements is thus 0.14 % ($k = 1$), to which we add the repeatability uncertainty recorded during the LNG measurements, i.e. $u_{repeat} = 0.019$ %, to obtain an on-site calibration uncertainty of 0.14 % ($k = 1$). We note that in this case there is no uncertainty due to the synchronization timing since the same data acquisition system has been used to record the measurement data of both instruments (i.e., the CMF and the facility's master meter). Furthermore, there is no uncertainty contribution due to the on-site density estimation since both the CMF and the facility's master meter measurement results are based on mass flow rate. The errors for LNG measurements are computed using the facility's references, with an associated standard uncertainty of 0.09 % ($k = 1$) (the facility has an uncertainty of 0.17 % ($k = 2$) for mass flow measurements). The comparison between the CMF measurement results and those of VSL's calibration facility show errors in the CMF's measurements between -0.23 % and -0.26 % (see Figure 3-1) with an associated standard uncertainty of 0.09 % ($k = 1$). These errors fall within the 95 % confidence interval identified by the uncertainty associated to the density model for LNG measurements, i.e. ± 0.28 % ($k = 2$), although they are rather close to the lower boundary of the confidence interval. Furthermore, we note that the errors have similar values for each setpoint and do not behave as a random error. We thus consider this error as a systematic effect in the CMF measurements and include an additional uncertainty source in the uncertainty budget for LH₂ measurements as described in subsection 3.3.4. Lastly, we remark that this conclusion is based on limited samples and additional testing is required to further investigate this behaviour.

The comparison of the LH₂ measurement results given by the turbine and the CMF meters reveals errors on totalized mass ranging from 2.0 % to 2.9 % with a standard uncertainty of about 0.67 % ($k = 1$). The error uncertainty does not explain the measured difference between the meters, revealing thus that this error is significantly different from zero and that the turbine meters tend to overestimate the flow rate with respect to the reference CMF measurements.

To conclude, this study indicates that, the achievable base standard uncertainty for LH₂ mass flow rate measurement by a CMF lies within range 0.2 % - 0.5 % relative (see section 3.3.3). This study further indicates that by combining alternative fluid calibrations and CMF modelling, it is possible to obtain an estimated uncertainty of 1.34 % ($k = 2$) on totalized mass when measuring the flow rate of liquefied hydrogen using volume based and mass based flow rate measurements (see Table 3-4). The main uncertainty source was identified as the on-site density estimation necessary to convert the volume flow measurements into mass flow measurements. The calibration uncertainty is likely to be lower when comparing meters both measuring mass (or volume) flow rate. The results indicate the need for reliable and accurate temperature measurements (the latter allowing for an accurate density estimate), so that volume based (turbine, ultrasonic) and mass based (Coriolis) amount measurements in LH₂ custody transfer processes can be compared with smaller uncertainties. This indication and the applicability of the alternative fluid calibration combined with the CMF meter model for LH₂ flow applications requires further proving by dedicated LNG and LH₂ flow standard, with direct link to the SI-units.

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

3.6 Acknowledgements

This project (20IND11 MetHyInfra) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. This project has received funding from the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy of the Netherlands. Martijn Boogaarts is acknowledged for on-site assistance during the LH₂ measurements.

3.7 Declaration of competing interest

M. Brugman and A. Druzhkov are employed by Emerson.

3.8 A Mathematical definition of the raw error

The raw error is calculated according to the following formula

$$e = \frac{Q_{cand} - Q_{ref}}{Q_{ref}}$$

where Q_{cand} and Q_{ref} are the totalized mass of the candidate and of the reference meter respectively. When comparing the two correction models, Q_{cand} is selected as the totalized mass obtained applying the stiffness correction model to the CMF's measurement results, while in the data processing for the on-site calibration Q_{cand} is given by the totalized mass measured by the combined turbine meters. In both cases Q_{ref} is given by the totalized mass measured by the CMF's measurement results corrected by means of the density method.

4 Measurement corrections for temperature effects in Coriolis mass flow meters for LH₂ applications²

The flow measuring characteristic of the Coriolis flow meter is typically defined as:

$$\Delta t = \frac{\Delta\phi}{\omega_n} = K_{flow} q_m, \quad (1)$$

where Δt is the time difference between the vibrational motions at two sensing points, equal to the ratio of the phase difference $\Delta\phi$ and the natural frequency $\omega_n = 2\pi f_n$, K_{flow} is the flow sensitivity and q_m is the mass flow rate of the measured fluid. K_{flow} depends on the structural and mechanical parameters of the measuring tube, so its value is also affected by the temperature of T , i.e. $K_{flow} = K_{flow}(T)$. Eq. (1) can be converted into the form of the measurement function for the mass flow rate as:

$$q_m = F_{cal} \Delta t, \quad (2)$$

where $F_{cal} = F_{cal}(T)$ is the temperature-dependent flow calibration factor. The flow calibration factor at the actual temperature $F_{cal}(T)$ can be defined as the product of the flow calibration factor at the reference temperature $F_{cal}(T_{ref})$ and the temperature correction factor $\xi(T)$:

$$F_{cal}(T) = \xi(T) F_{cal}(T_{ref}), \quad (3)$$

where $\xi(T)$ accounts for relative effects on the flow calibration factor as the temperature changes from T_{ref} to T .

The aim of the related WP4 activity was to evaluate the typical temperature correction models used in Coriolis flow meters. Since temperature effects also design dependent, we selected three different design configurations of the measuring tubes for the analysis: the U-tube, the arc tube and the straight tube, as shown in Figure 4-1. The curved parts of the U-tube and the arc tube represent half of the total length along the tube centreline. The flow meters operate in the first (out-of-plane) bending mode, which corresponds to the lowest natural frequency. Harmonic excitation occurs at the node E at the centre of the tube length. The vibrational signals are sensed at the nodes S1 and S2 in the centre of each half of the tube.

All the designs are assumed to have the same tube material (SS 316 stainless steel), the same tube cross-section ($D_i(T_{ref}) = 20$ mm and $D_o(T_{ref}) = 22$ mm), and the same length along the tube centreline ($L_{tube}(T_{ref}) = 600$ mm); these dimensional data are given at $T_{ref} = 293$ K. The material data considered for SS 316 for Young's modulus $E(T)$, shear modulus $G(T)$ and thermal strain $\varepsilon_{th}(T)$ are from Costa et al. [9] and NIST [19]. The cross-sectional dimensions at the temperature T are defined as $D_i(T) = D_i(T_{ref})(1 + \varepsilon_{th}(T))$ and $D_o(T) = D_o(T_{ref})(1 + \varepsilon_{th}(T))$. The change of length of each beam FE

² This chapter of the deliverable contains a summary of the analysis and findings regarding the evaluation of the correction models for temperature effects in Coriolis flow meters, which is presented in more detail in the paper submitted for publication in January 2024 [33].

from $L(T_{ref})$ to $L(T)$ results from the static analysis. The density $\rho_t(T)$ is considered in such a way that the law of conservation of mass applies and $\rho_t(T_{ref}) = 7960 \text{ kg/m}^3$ for SS 316 material.

The analysis presented in this report has an emphasis on the success of the temperature correction at LH₂ conditions at 20 K. As a reference value in the evaluation, we use the simulation results with the numerical finite element (FE) model based on the Timoshenko beam theory and one-dimensional fluid flow. Special emphasis in the modelling was placed on the appropriate inclusion of temperature effects, both those resulting from the temperature-dependent elastic properties of the measuring tube and those related to thermal strains and stresses in the measuring tube. Section 4.1 shortly describes the four investigated temperature correction models, referred to as the correction models A, B, C and D and Section 0 presents the results and discusses the advantages and limitations of the temperature correction models.

Figure 4-1: Selected configurations of the measuring tubes for the simulation study. Vibrational excitation occurs at the point E, vibrational signals are sensed at the points S1 and S2.

4.1 Temperature correction models

4.1.1 Correction model A

Temperature correction model A is based on the predictions of temperature effects by flow calibration at different temperatures near ambient conditions and extrapolation to cryogenic temperatures. In a relatively narrow temperature range near $T_{ref} = 293 \text{ K}$, the temperature correction factor can be assumed to be linearly dependent on temperature:

$$\xi_A(T) = \frac{F_{cal}(T)}{F_{cal}(T_{ref})} = 1 + K_\xi(T - T_{ref}), \quad (4)$$

where K_ξ is the temperature sensitivity coefficient. In this paper, the coefficient K_ξ was determined by water flow simulations at two temperatures $T_1 = T_{ref} = 293 \text{ K}$ and $T_2 = 283 \text{ K}$.

4.1.2 Correction model B

Temperature correction model B is based on a physical model for the dependence of the flow calibration factor F_{cal} on Young's modulus E and thermal strain ε_{th} of the measuring tube, as well as

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

on further consideration of experimental data on the temperature dependence of these material properties:

$$\xi_B(T) = \frac{F_{cal}(T)}{F_{cal}(T_{ref})} = \xi_E(T) \xi_{\varepsilon_{th}}(T), \quad (5)$$

where:

$$\xi_E(T) = \frac{E(T)}{E(T_{ref})}, \quad (6)$$

$$\xi_{\varepsilon_{th}}(T) = 1 + \varepsilon_{th}(T). \quad (7)$$

4.1.3 Correction model C

Temperature correction model C takes into account the effects related to Young's modulus $E(T)$ and thermal strain $\varepsilon_{th}(T)$ as in the model B, but additionally predicts the remaining effects due to the Poisson's ratio $\mu(T)$ of the measuring tube by using flow calibration results near ambient conditions and extrapolating to cryogenic temperatures:

$$\xi_C(T) = \frac{F_{cal}(T)}{F_{cal}(T_{ref})} = \xi_E(T) \xi_{\varepsilon_{th}}(T) \xi_{\mu}(T), \quad (8)$$

where $\xi_E(T)$ and $\xi_{\varepsilon_{th}}(T)$ are equal as in Eqs. (6) and (7), respectively, and $\xi_{\mu}(T)$ is determined empirically as a function of $\mu(T)$:

$$\xi_{\mu}(T) = 1 + K_{\mu}(\mu(T) - \mu(T_{ref})), \quad (9)$$

where K_{μ} is the related sensitivity coefficient. In this paper, the coefficient K_{μ} was determined by the water flow simulations at two temperatures $T_1 = T_{ref} = 293$ K and $T_2 = 283$ K.

4.1.4 Correction model D

Temperature correction model D considers the effects of temperature dependent Young's modulus $E(T)$ and thermal strain $\varepsilon_{th}(T)$, which, unlike in the model B, are determined from the effect of temperature on the natural frequency f_n :

$$\xi_D(T) = \frac{F_{cal}(T)}{F_{cal}(T_{ref})} = \xi_E(T) \xi_{\varepsilon_{th}}(T) = \frac{[C_2 + \rho_f \xi_{\varepsilon_{th}}(T)^3] f_n^2}{C_1}, \quad (10)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are the calibration constants. The application of the correction model D requires knowledge of the fluid density ρ_f at observed temperature conditions. In this paper, the calibration constants C_1 and C_2 have been determined from the fluid density measuring characteristic by the water and air simulations at $T_{ref} = 293$ K:

$$C_1 = \frac{\rho_{f,water} - \rho_{f,air}}{\frac{1}{f_{n1,water}^2} - \frac{1}{f_{n1,air}^2}}, \quad C_2 = \frac{C_1}{f_{n1,water}^2} - \rho_{f,water}. \quad (11)$$

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

4.2 Results

The results of the temperature correction factors at the LH₂ temperature of 20 K predicted by the four correction models, A, B, C and D, and their relative errors from the FE model reference value are summarised in Table 4-1 for all three tube designs under study.

Table 4-1: Temperature correction factors at the LH₂ temperature of 20 K predicted by the correction models A, B, C and D and their relative errors from the FE model reference value (in brackets), for the three tube designs under study.

	U-tube	Arc tube	Straight tube
$\xi^{(FEM)}$	1.0702	1.0735	1.3294
ξ_A	1.1097 (+3.7 %)	1.1145 (+3.8 %)	1.4484 (+9.0 %)
ξ_B	1.0637 (−0.61 %)	1.0637 (−0.92 %)	1.0637 (−20.0 %)
ξ_C	1.0706 (+0.03 %)	1.0747 (+0.11 %)	1.3612 (+2.4 %)
ξ_D	1.0653 (−0.46 %)	1.0794 (+0.55 %)	1.5696 (+18.1 %)

The correction model A, based on a linear extrapolation of the temperature effect determined at ambient temperatures to cryogenic temperatures, shows positive prediction errors. They result from non-linearities in the material properties of the measuring tube, which become very dominant in the temperature range below 150 K. In the case of the curved tubes, the main cause is a non-linear temperature dependence of Young's modulus, which leads to a prediction error of about 4 % at 20 K. In the case of the straight tube, the non-linear temperature dependence of thermal strain and the resulting thermal stress are added, resulting in a prediction error of the model A of 9 % at 20 K.

The correction model B, based on the implementation of empirical data for temperature variations of Young's modulus and thermal strain, shows negative prediction errors. The prediction errors at 20 K are −0.61 % and −0.92 % for the U-tube and the arc tube, respectively, rising to −20 % for the straight tube. The remaining prediction errors of the model B are mainly related to the effects not taken into account, such as those related to Poisson's ratio and thermal stress, the former being greater for the curved tubes and the latter for the straight tube.

The correction model C adds the Poisson's ratio effect to the correction model B, the sensitivity coefficient of which is determined by flow calibration close to the ambient conditions. It should be emphasised that such an empirical estimate of the model for the Poisson's ratio related correction factor captures all the remaining temperature effects near ambient conditions, e.g. in addition to the Poisson's ratio effect, also the effects of internal stresses. However, when extrapolating these effects to the cryogenic temperature range, certain differences arise because this extrapolation assumes that these effects vary as a function of the Poisson's ratio (which is fully true only for the Poisson's ratio effect, but not for the thermal stress effect). The prediction errors of the model C are very promising for the curved tubes, 0.03 % for the U-tube and 0.11 % for the arc tube, but are still relatively large at 2.4 % for the straight tube.

However, it is important to be aware of the limitations of the presented methods. The uncertainty of the prediction of the correction factors by the models B and C is directly influenced by the uncertainty of the material properties used in the correction models, i.e. the uncertainties of $E(T)$, $\varepsilon_{th}(T)$ and $\mu(T)$. A potentially large contribution can also be expected for the uncertainty in the empirical determination of the sensitivity coefficient K_μ , since the effects involved are relatively small in a

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

narrow temperature range, e.g. about 0.03 % per 10 K for the U-tube design close to ambient conditions.

These uncertainty contributions are eliminated to some extent by the model D, which is based on a different correction principle. The correction model D takes into account the effects of Young's modulus and thermal strain, $\xi_E(T)\xi_{\text{eth}}(T)$, through the effect of temperature on the natural frequency. The model D does not require knowledge of Young's modulus to determine the correction, but it requires the fluid density to be known. However, it does require knowledge of thermal strain to correct for contraction effects on the density measuring characteristic, but this influence is about an order of magnitude smaller than on the flow measuring characteristic. The prediction errors of the model D are -0.46% for the U-tube and 0.55% for the arc tube, but they are still very large at 18.1% for the straight tube. The uncertainty in the prediction of the correction factor by the model D depends on the uncertainty of the fluid density calibration and the natural frequency measurements.

5 PTB vaporisation method report

5.1 Introduction

The calibration of meters for use with gaseous or particularly liquid hydrogen is not only accompanied by safety issues but also by environmental challenges. Consequently, the MetHyInfra Project concentrated on developing a method to use alternative fluids, such as water, liquid nitrogen and/or liquid helium instead. In general, the objective was to test and calibrate the meter with these fluids. Subsequently, the performance and the uncertainty associated with the measurements would be evaluated through traceable measurements with hydrogen.

The specific goal of the activities addressed in this report was to investigate whether flow sensors can be calibrated at ambient conditions and subsequently used at cryogenic temperatures which may arise when liquid hydrogen is transferred. Therefore, a calibration method known as the “vaporisation method”, which is traceable to the International System of Units (SI) through the use of Laminar Flow Elements (LFE), was applied. The method is described in detail in the subsequent section. The flow rates were relatively low, with values typically below 4 kg/h. A commercially available Coriolis meter, suitable for cryogenic conditions was used. Prior to the measurements the Coriolis meter was calibrated with water and air at ambient conditions. Due to safety regulations, direct measurements at cryogenic conditions could not be performed with liquid hydrogen. Alternatively, liquid nitrogen (LN₂) and liquid helium (LHe) were used. This report presents a summary of the used equipment, experiments conducted, experiences gained, results obtained, and an estimation of the measurement uncertainty and potential of this method.

5.2 Experimental Setup

The fundamental experimental setup is shown in Figure 5-1 and will be described in greater detail in the subsequent sections. The operational principle of this setup can be summarized as follows. An alternative cryogenic fluid flows from a cryogenic storage vessel through a vacuum insulated chamber equipped with temperature sensors and the installed Meter Under Test (MUT). In this instance, liquid nitrogen and helium was used instead of hydrogen for safety reasons. Subsequently, the cryogenic liquid is conveyed into a heat exchanger where it is vaporised. In the final step, the gas flow is measured by LFEs to ensure SI-traceability. Due to the conservation of mass, the MUT can be tested or calibrated.

Figure 5-1: Schematic setup of the vaporisation method.

5.2.1 Meter under Test

The used meter under test was a RHM03 Coriolis meter from RHEONIK with the following specifications:

- Maximum operating pressure: 160 bar @ 50°C
- Housing material: stainless steel

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

- Nominal flowrate: 2.5 kg/min
- Nominal diameter: 8 mm
- Temperature range: -270 °C - +50 °C
- Dimensions: 120 x 240 mm
- Installation: thin PTFE insulated cables

The Coriolis meter was calibrated by the manufacturer against a master flow meter on a warm water test rig at two different flow points, with an expanded uncertainty of 0.05 % ($k = 2$). The device is equipped with a special housing designed for operation in vacuum conditions. The Coriolis meter includes several apertures, to enable evacuation, and prevent the occurrence of virtual leaks. The vacuum housing and the original meter are shown in Figure 5-2.

Following delivery, the meter was calibrated and tested with water and compressed air at different departments of PTB. The results of these experiments are presented in section 5.3.

Figure 5-2: RHEONIK Coriolis RHM03 (MUT) with vacuum housing (left) and installed temperature sensors (right; tube: 1, cross: 2).

The Coriolis meter data was logged using the RHEComPro software, provided by RHEONIK. The following parameters were recorded during the experiments:

- Time: The current time of the PC, on which the software is installed
- MassFlowRate (no cut off): The raw mass flow rate signal without any internal corrections
- Assurance Factor: The stability factor of the meter performance, as determined by RHEONIK
- TubeMeanTemp: Temperature of the tube of the Coriolis, as shown in Figure 5-2, right, number 1
- TorBarMeanTemp: Temperature of the cross of the Coriolis Figure 5-2, right, number 2

The meter was installed using small PTFE plates with finger contacts inside the cryogenic part of the vaporization test rig, as shown in Figure 5-3. The plates were installed to stabilize the meter position and to avoid tension and torque in the installation.

Figure 5-3: Installed Coriolis inside of the vaporisation test rig.

5.2.2 Vaporisation test rig

The used vaporisation test rig was developed by the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) and was made available by PTB for the MethHyInfra project. The cryogenic measuring section is divided into three distinct sections. The first section is the cryogenic measuring section, which includes the MUT, as shown in Figure 5-4 on the left. The second component is the heat exchanger, where the cryogenic liquid is vaporised. The third section is the gaseous section, which includes the reference LFEs (see Figure 5-4 on the right).

Figure 5-4: Vaporisation test rig.

The schematic structure of the test rig is shown in Figure 5-5, which also includes the sensor system of the test rig. The cryogenic liquid is provided to the system via either a vacuum insulated liquid helium lifter (maximum operating pressure 0.5 bar gauge) or a regular liquid nitrogen withdrawal device (maximum operating pressure 1.5 bar gauge). Firstly, the fluid is guided through a Venturi tube³ and a subsequent perforated plate rectifier with the objective of ensuring uniform temperature mixing and homogeneous flow. Two TVO sensors are used to measure the temperature of the pipe before and after this flow conditioning. A third TVO sensor is located inside the tube, in direct contact with the medium to assess the temperature of the cryogenic liquid. In the subsequent section of the cryogenic part, the MUT is installed. Subsequently, the cryogenic liquid is conveyed into the vaporiser, which is

³ The Venturi tube is part of the test rig and was not removed to avoid leakages in the test line. The Venturi was not used as a measurement device in this setup.

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

essentially a heat exchanger that is maintained at a temperature of 30 °C. The temperature of the water bath was monitored with a platinum resistance thermometer (Pt100). The final section is the measurement of mass flow at room temperature, using the existing system, which comprises of ball valves, LFEs and pressure transmitters.

The flow rate inside the system could not be regulated neither accurately nor repeatable due to the lack of necessary hardware installation at the entrance of the system. In general, the driving force for the flow is the pressure difference inside the cryogenic storage vessel. It is possible to regulate the mass flow to a certain extent by adjusting the overpressure, which can be achieved by utilising the cryogenic needle valve, which is part of the liquid helium lifter, or the ball valve of the liquid nitrogen withdrawal device.

Figure 5-5: Schematic structure of the vaporisation test rig.

5.3 Conducted Experiments

This section presents a summary of the experiments conducted as part of the MethHyInfra project. Prior to the cryogenic measurements, all relevant meters and installations were tested. The MUT was calibrated using compressed air and water. Additionally, the LFEs were calibrated with compressed air.

5.3.1 MUT calibrations

5.3.1.1 Compressed air

The meter was installed at the dry compressed air calibration test rig at PTB. The flow was controlled by means of critical flow venturi nozzles (CFVN), while the corresponding inlet pressure was regulated by a high precision pressure controller. The schematic structure of the setup is shown in Figure 5-6.

The initial calibration was carried out over a flow rate range from 0.6 kg/h up to 6 kg/h. The expanded uncertainty of the calibration is 0.2 % ($k = 2$). The measurements were performed at a room temperature of $(20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C})$ without additional temperature stabilisation. The reference for the calibrations is a master meter (rotary piston meter, REF), which is directly traceable to SI-units. The measurement error was calculated using equation Eq. 5-1.

$$e = \frac{Q_{m,MUT} - Q_{m,REF}}{Q_{m,REF}} * 100 \% \quad \text{Eq. 5-1}$$

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

Figure 5-6: Schematic structure of the initial compressed air calibration of the MUT.

The MUT was measured upstream and downstream with 3 repetitions per flow point. The campaign was repeated three times. For all experiments the internal cut-off value of the meter was deactivated. It was observed, that setting the zero point of the Coriolis meter led to different zero values at the same conditions. The value varied between -0.05 kg/h and -0.085 kg/h . In response to the inherent instability of zero values, a procedural adjustment was implemented whereby the zero point was not established but rather documented both preceding and following each measurement iteration. Subsequently, the flow was adjusted in accordance with the recorded zero values. All values presented herein are based on the aforementioned corrected values.

The values of the three repetitions of each measurement campaign are shown in Figure 5-7 with error e over mass flow rate Q_m . The colours indicate the operating mode (upstream or downstream), whereas the shape of the plotted points indicates the individual measurement campaign. It can be observed that the deviation to the calibration by the manufacturer increases particularly below 1.5 kg/h .

The mean error curve of the MUT calibrated with dry air is shown in Figure 5-8. The increasing deviation at lower flow rates is accompanied by larger uncertainty bars, which indicate the standard deviation of the mean value for each measurement point. Nevertheless, all results are within the expanded uncertainty (green band in Figure 5-8, $U = 0.2 \%$, $k = 2$) of the test bench.

Figure 5-7: Measurement results of the initial dry gas calibration.

Figure 5-8: The red dots and corresponding uncertainty bars indicate the mean values of the dry air calibration together with their standard deviation respectively. The expanded uncertainty of the PTB test rig is indicated by the green band ($U = 0.2$, $k = 2$)

From the error curve in Figure 5-8 it can be seen that the MUT has a roughly constant offset of approximately +0.82 %.

5.3.1.2 Water

In addition to the dry gas calibration, the meter was calibrated at the low water flow facility at PTB's department 1.5 "Liquid Flow". Due to the limitations of the test rig, the calibration was carried out in increments of 0.5 kg/h, from 1 kg/h up to 6 kg/h. The measurements were performed at ambient conditions with a constant inlet pressure of 2 bar. The schematic setup is shown in Figure 5-9. The flow through the MUT was maintained at a constant flow rate. For each individual measuring point the diverter was switched over and the medium to be measured was fed onto the weighing scale. Due to SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

the limitations of the test rig, it was not possible to record the zero value before each point, in contrast to the air calibration. The zero point was only recorded before and after the complete measurement programme in order to correct the mass flow of the Coriolis meter accordingly.

Figure 5-9: Schematic structure of the initial water calibration of the MUT.

Analogous to the dry gas calibration, the water calibration was carried out at both the upstream and downstream locations. The measurements at each flow point were repeated 5 times. The individual deviations were calculated using equation 5.1 and are shown in Figure 5-10 as the error e in percent. The colour of the symbol indicates the operational mode during the calibration. The deviations increase with lower flow rate, with the highest values observed at 1 kg/h.

Figure 5-10: Errors from the calibration at PTBs water testbench.

The mean error curve of the MUT calibrated with water is shown in Figure 5-11. The uncertainty bars indicate the standard deviation of the mean value for the individual measurement point. All values are within the expanded uncertainty of the test rig of 0.2 % ($k = 2$).

Figure 5-11: The red squares indicate the mean values of the errors and their corresponding standard deviation which were derived from the measurement results of the water calibration at PTBs test rig. The expanded uncertainty ($U = 0.2$, $k = 2$) of the test rig is displayed as green band.

5.3.1.3 Summary

The comparative analysis between the outcomes of the initial dry air calibration and the subsequent water calibration demonstrates notable disparities that exceed the threshold of expanded uncertainties, as depicted in Figure 5-12. These disparities accentuate with smaller flow rates, particularly in relation to the MetHyInfra project objective. Conversely, at higher flow rates exceeding 4.5 kg/h, both datasets exhibit a satisfactory level of concordance. The observed deviation at the lowest flow rate was predictable, attributed to the deliberate oversizing of the meter to mitigate excessive pressure drop across the apparatus. It is noteworthy that flow rates below 2.5 kg/h fall substantially below the meter's Q_{min} threshold, resulting in the loss of linearity. Taking the different calibrations into account, a constant error correction of 1.17% was determined to be applicable to the measured flow rate. A corresponding expanded uncertainty of the Coriolis meter of 0.7 % ($k = 2$) was assigned, while it is recommended that the meter should not be used for mass flow rates below 1.5 kg/h.

Figure 5-12: Mean error curves of the compressed dry air gas calibration, the water calibration and the water calibration at the manufacturer together with the corresponding repeatability.

5.3.2 Laminar Flow Elements (LFEs)

In order to measure the mass flow in the gas phase (Part 3 in Figure 5-4), SI-traceable laminar flow elements (LFEs) were used as a reference. LFEs are devices designed to accurately measure and control the flow of fluids, particularly gases and liquids. The operation of these devices is based on the principle of laminar flow, whereby fluid particles move in parallel layers with minimal mixing between them. This characteristic behaviour enables precise flow measurement by exploiting the relationship between pressure drop and flow rate within laminar flow regimes.

5.3.2.1 Construction and Design

The LFEs used comprise a straight, cylindrical tube with a precisely calibrated diameter and length. The tube is manufactured from stainless steel in order to ensure stability and durability. Within this tube, a carefully engineered restriction, such as a porous plug or capillary tube, is installed. This restriction induces laminar flow conditions by suppressing turbulent fluctuations in the fluid stream.

5.3.2.2 Working principle

When a fluid flows through a laminar flow element, it experiences a pressure drop across the restriction due to viscous effects. This pressure drop is directly proportional to the flow rate according to Poiseuille's law, which governs laminar flow in cylindrical conduits. By measuring the pressure difference before and after the restriction, the flow rate can be determined precisely and fully traceable to SI-units.

The laminar flow regime ensures that the fluid velocity profile remains parabolic, with the highest velocity occurring at the centre of the tube and decreasing towards the walls. This velocity distribution allows for accurate flow measurement since it is not affected by turbulent fluctuations that could distort the readings. Furthermore, LFEs exhibit a linear relationship between pressure drop and flow rate, which simplifies the calibration and interpretation of measurements. The LFEs used for the experimental part were initially calibrated with dry air, with the linear relationship between the mass flow and the pressure drop subsequently calculated. This linearisation is a common and valid simplification.

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

5.3.2.3 Calibration

The reference to ensure the SI traceability for the LFE calibration were the critical flow venturi nozzles (CFVNs). The inlet pressure is regulated to generate different flow rates. The differential pressure over the LFEs is then measured and used to generate the working function.

Figure 5-13: Schematic structure of the initial dry air calibration of the LFE.

Each LFE was calibrated within the pressure range of 5 mbar to 25 mbar, which is a standard range typically employed for LFE calibration. The calibration outcomes are illustrated in Figure 5-14. It is notable that the standard deviation was omitted from the plot due to its negligible magnitude, which was less than 1×10^{-3} for these assessments. This value is smaller than the symbols utilised for visualisation. Despite the logarithmic scaling on the y-axis, it is notable that the calibration results enabled the execution of linear regression analysis for each LFE.

Figure 5-14: Dry air calibration results of the LFEs used within the vaporisation test rig. Y-axis with logarithmic scale.

The linear interpolation has the following form:

$$f(x) = m \cdot x + n \quad \text{Eq. 5-2}$$

The corresponding fit coefficients are shown in

Table 5-1 together with their standard uncertainties.

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

Table 5-1: LFE linear interpolation including coefficient of determination.

Name	y-Intersection		Gradient		Statistic
	n	uncertainty	m	uncertainty	coefficient of determination
LAM 3.5-10-1.1	0.01316	0.00299	0.02288	0.00018	0.99936
LAM 10-10-2.8	0.04882	0.00928	0.06487	0.00057	0.99923
LAM 25-10-1.5	0.20674	0.02689	0.17060	0.00165	0.99906
LAM 75-5-2.11	4.87599	0.36278	0.47542	0.02131	0.97833
LAM-ES 1-10-1.1	0.00074	0.00031	0.00654	0.00002	0.99992
LAM-ES 150-5/8.1	10.10865	0.62298	0.97701	0.03821	0.98491

5.3.3 Cryogenic experiments

The cryogenic experiments were carried out in two distinct phases. In the initial phase, measurements were conducted using liquid nitrogen. Subsequently, liquid helium was used in phase two. The experiments with nitrogen were primarily used to test the system, the sensors, to establish a test sequence and to obtain preliminary results. However, in order to reach temperatures comparable to those of liquid hydrogen (about 24 K), liquid helium (4.2 K) is required.

5.3.3.1 Liquid nitrogen (LN₂)

As previously outlined in 0, the cryogenic liquid was provided by a liquid nitrogen withdrawal device, with the outlet being directly connected to the inlet of the test rig. The maximum operating pressure was 1.5 bar gauge. The measurement run started with the initial cooling of the system until the thermal equilibrium was reached at the MUT. This corresponds to a temperature of about -192 °C, which varies according to the operating pressure.

Once the required measurement conditions were reached, the zero point of the Coriolis meter had to be determined. Unfortunately, the setup did not permit the performance of standing start-stop measurements, due to the absence of a cryogenic valve. Consequently, the valve of the LN₂ withdrawal device had to be used. Once this valve was closed, the remaining LN₂ in the connecting hose was vaporized, displacing the nitrogen in the cryogenic section. This resulted in a change of temperature, despite the flow of LN₂ not actually being stopped. In order to estimate the required zero point, the following procedure was employed.

The outlet valve of the withdrawal device was closed. Figure 5-15 displays the temporal interval between the closure of the valve and its subsequent reopening. As previous stated, an increase in temperature (about 40 K) was observed during a period of unstable flow. The blue vertical lines indicate the timeframe that was used for the zero point determination. It is assumed that at this point the LN₂ in the hose has been completely vaporised and the flow through the MUT has ceased. Then, a linear interpolation as shown in Figure 5-16 was applied.

Figure 5-15: Flow and temperature data of the MUT after the valve was closed.

Figure 5-16 Linear interpolation of the zero -point of the MUT as a function of temperature and the corresponding fit coefficients including their standard uncertainty.

This correlation enabled the determination of the zero point of the MUT at the corresponding measuring temperature by extrapolation. This estimation of the zero point contributes 1.5 % ($k = 2$) to the overall expanded uncertainty of the mass flow rate and is, thus, the dominant component at this point. The flow signal of the Coriolis meter was corrected with the extrapolated zero point and using the calibration determined in section 5.3.1. Subsequently, the mass flows were compared to the gas flow measured by the LFEs after vaporisation. The results of the 4 measurements can be seen in Table 5-2 including their combined uncertainties.

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

Table 5-2: Measurement results LN₂

Date	Nr.	Time [s]	Temperature		Flow		error [%]
			MUT [°C]	LFE [°C]	MUT [kg/h]	LFE [kg/h]	
16.01.2023	M1	180	-191.83	18.20	2.269 ± 1.7 %	2.273 ± 0.2 %	-0.117
17.01.2023	M2	3600	-192.47	17.19	2.094 ± 1.7 %	2.087 ± 0.2 %	0.356
18.01.2023	M3	1800	-192.61	16.51	2.650 ± 1.7 %	3.037 ± 0.2 %	-11.729
19.01.2023	M4	1500	-193.45	16.15	2.024 ± 1.7 %	2.005 ± 0.2 %	-0.793

The relative deviations between MUT and LFE typically range from -0.8 % to 0.4 % and agree on the level of the standard uncertainty. However, the value M3 with the highest flow rate shows a significant larger deviation of more than 10 %. This is likely a consequence of a small leak, which tended to occur at higher flow rates that demanded higher operation pressures. It is likely that the KF-connectors, which were used for the LN₂ supply are the source of the leaks. This is because the test rig is equipped with a KF50 flange on the inlet side. Despite the use of indium seals, it was not possible to fully eliminate the leaks at higher pressures. The leaks were detected by small visual differences in the ice layer, as shown in Figure 5-17.

Figure 5-17: Leakage detection via ice layer of the system

5.3.3.2 Liquid helium (LHe)

Following the tests with LN₂, the fluid was changed to liquid helium. Unfortunately, it was not possible to reach the liquid phase of helium at the MUT. After the initial cooling of the system the lowest temperature achieved was -267 °C, rather than the anticipated -269 °C. It is assumed that the electric wiring between the MUT and the electric feedthrough of the vacuum chamber was of an excessive mass and relatively short, and thus acted as a thermal bridge. Furthermore, the heat generated by the comparatively large Coriolis meter could be excessive. This assumption is based on the observation that the temperature measured by the TVOs steadily increased from the inlet of the LHe towards the MUT. Unfortunately, as shown in Figure 5-17, it was not possible to maintain a constant flow rate with LHe.

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

The graph shows the flow data of the MUT over time, accompanied by the calculated mass flow of a LFE. The flow rate data of the LFE is generally consistent with the MUT. Furthermore, the agreement between the MUT and the LFE LAM25-10-1.5 (red line) is within a margin of error of $\pm 2\%$.

At this point, it is not possible to ascertain the reason for the inability to generate constant flow rates. The LHe storage cans apply a constant internal heating process to maintain the operating pressure, which precludes the possibility of manually adjusting the operating pressure. The only means of influencing the flow rate was through the cryogenic needle valves. As shown in Figure 5-18, the heating phase of the LHe storage cans is marked in light magenta.

The helium was fed to a large yellow helium storage balloon, which is part of the helium recovery system and partially visible in Figure 5-4. Its inflation is likely to have generated a non-constant back pressure. Once the balloon reached its maximum capacity, the helium gas was compressed and fed to the helium liquefier, which is located in a separate building on the campus. It was not possible to maintain the larger flow rates for an extended period of time, as the compressor was started manually, but the balloon continued to inflate. The helium recovery phases during the experiment are shown as light cyan areas in Figure 5-8. It can be observed that only during relatively short periods of time neither the heating nor the helium recovery phase was active.

Figure 5-18: Flow data of the MUT and two different laminar flow elements over time

During this short interval, the mass flow deviation between the MUT and the LFE is below $\pm 0.1\%$ (see

Table 5-3). Nevertheless, this outcome cannot be confirmed, as the prevailing situation could not be reproduced due to limitation of measurement time.

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

Table 5-3: Measurement results LHe

Date	Nr.	Time [s]	Temperature		Flow		error [%]
			MUT [°C]	LFE [°C]	MUT [kg/h]	LFE [kg/h]	
23.02.2023	M1	600	-266.12	21.09	2.947 ± 1.7 %	2.948 ± 0.2 %	-0.034

5.4 Summary and Conclusion

The investigations conducted within the MetHyInfra project have demonstrated a significant potential for calibrating the Meter Under Test (MUT), which is intended for use in cryogenic liquids at ambient conditions. Nevertheless, it is important to note that certain limitations must be taken into account:

1. **MUT:**

The utilized Coriolis meter exhibited a deviation between the initial calibration with water and the subsequent calibration with dry gas. This discrepancy is primarily a consequence of the oversizing of the meter for the intended flow range. However, the selection of a larger meter was driven by the concern that the pressure loss at lower flow rates might not adequately compensate for the low inlet pressure. It is important to note that the selected meter size was not optimal for the intended experiments.

Furthermore, the stability of the meter's zero point represents a significant challenge. Despite efforts to ensure reproducibility, achieving a consistent zero point under stable conditions proved unattainable. Consequently, the approach of recording the zero point before and after each measurement was favoured, although this introduced further limitations concerning the vaporization test rig.

With regards to the measurements conducted with LHe, further investigations are required to clarify the reasons why the liquid phase of helium was not reached at the MUT. As previously stated it is hypothesized that the wiring or the generated heat from the operation of the oversized Coriolis meter are the probable causes.

2. **Vaporisation test rig:**

The test rig, which was developed and used by KIT for use with critical flow Venturi nozzles (CFVNs), demonstrates potential for the evaluation of Coriolis meters under cryogenic conditions. However, further optimisation of the setup could enhance the efficacy for this particular application. The incorporation of an additional cryogenic valve before the MUT, in conjunction with a pressure relief valve at the inlet, and the possibility of cryogenic pressure measurement would improve the determination of the zero point in conjunction with testing a Coriolis meter.

In conclusion, it is evident that the desired objectives within the MetHyInfra project were not fully achieved for the vaporization method. The performance of the test rig with liquid helium (LHe) did not meet expectations, as single-phase LHe was not adequately delivered to the meter. Nevertheless, the vaporisation concept proved successful with liquid nitrogen (LN₂). The potential offered by the vaporisation method remains viable for future applications, provided that appropriate adjustments are made to both the installation and the MUT. It is noteworthy that the stability and support of low temperatures presented significant challenges. Given that LH₂ operates at slightly higher temperatures compared to LHe, cooling with LHe is a viable option in the event that only limited quantities of LH₂ are available for the experiments. Furthermore, a system operating at a higher pressure offers greater flexibility for working with LH₂.

5.5 Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Joint Research Project (JRP) “Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows”. This project (20IND11 MetHyInfra) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

We would also like to thank Holger Neumann and Ralph Lietzow from the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) for providing the vaporization test rig shown in Figure 5-4.

In addition, we thank the colleagues from PTB department 7.5 for the location, 1.4 for the gaseous flow calibration, 1.5 for the water flow calibration and 7.4 for infrastructure and technical support.

6 Cryogenic LDV primary standard: modification for LH₂

The cryogenic LDV (Laser Doppler Velocimetry) measurement package is composed of three main sections: (1) the cryogenic seeding part, (2) the conditioning part with the measuring cross-section and (3) the divergent. The Figure 6-1 is a schematic of the cryogenic standard.

Figure 6-1: Schematic of the cryogenic LDV standard.

The seeding part is equipped with an access point for the seeding probes in cryogenic conditions, as well as two windows for the visualization of particles. The conditioning part is equipped with windows that permit the passage of laser beams for the measurement of the velocity profile at the exit of the convergent. The downstream part of the cryogenic LDV measurement package contains the divergent. The three aforementioned parts are located inside a vacuum chamber, which serves to provide a thermal insulation. For further details, please refer to Maury *et al.* [30]. The LDV standard has been modified to be LH₂-ready. The dimensions of the LDV standard have been modified to meet the requirements from the liquefied hydrogen refilling. It is anticipated that the mass flow will be about 5 t/h. The inner diameter of the standard was reduced from DN80 to DN50 (2 inches) at the inlet, while in the centre part of the measuring system, the diameter was reduced from DN40 to DN25 (1 inch; see Figure 6-2 below).

Figure 6-2: Schematic of the modification of the cryogenic LDV standard for being LH₂ ready.

The shrinking of equipment as the temperature reduces to liquefied hydrogen conditions (-253 °C) must be handled properly. In order to accommodate the shrinking, additional expansion joints have been incorporated into the external layer. Furthermore, the ATEX sensors currently installed had to be replaced in order to meet the ATEX ranking compliancy for LH₂ (i.e. IIC). The pressure and temperature sensors mounted on the cryogenic LDV standard are appropriately marked and have corresponding range for the measurements. Figure 6-3 below shows the LH₂ cryogenic LDV package:

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

Figure 6-3: Schematic of the modifications of the cryogenic LDV standard for being LH₂ ready.

7 Summary

7.1 SI-traceable LH₂ flow measurement uncertainty

The stated measurement uncertainty for the LH₂ flow objective of the project is “target uncertainty 0.3 % to 0.8 %”.

The method based on the transferability of water and LNG calibrations to LH₂ conditions (Chapter 3) concludes that “this study indicates that, the achievable base standard uncertainty for LH₂ mass flow rate measurement by a Coriolis mass flow meter (CMF) lies within the range of 0.2 % to 0.5 % relative”, which corresponds to 0.4 % to 1.0 % ($k = 2$) of the reference mass flow rate. It can be concluded, that the measurement uncertainty of the objective is approximately met. However, it is necessary to demonstrate that the estimated measurement uncertainty is corroborated by a dedicated flow standard with direct traceability to SI-units.

The measurement uncertainty associated with the measurement of LH₂ flow when utilising a master meter is dependent on the specific type of flow meter. A variety of master meter types were initially considered for the project (Coriolis, ultrasonic, and differential pressure devices). A survey of project’s consortium stakeholders revealed the availability and suitability of turbine and Coriolis flow meters for measuring LH₂ flows. In the on-site experiment described in chapter 3, the turbine meter LH₂ flow measurements were compared with the Coriolis meter LH₂ flow measurements. As the former measures volume flow rate (m³/h) and the latter mass flow (kg/h), it is necessary to determine the on-site density (kg/m³) in order to convert one to the other. Consequently, it was concluded in chapter 3 that “by combining alternative fluid calibrations and CMF modelling, it is possible to obtain an estimated uncertainty of 1.34 % ($k = 2$) on totalized mass when measuring the flow rate of liquefied hydrogen using volume based and mass-based flow rate measurements”. The errors observed ranged from 2.0 % to 2.9 %. Given the estimated uncertainty of 1.34 % ($k = 2$), it was therefore stated that “this error is significantly different from zero and ... [that] the turbine meters tend to overestimate the flow rate with respect to the reference CMF measurements”. In practice, such errors will not be noted or adjusted without calibration by an SI-traceable standard. This indicates that the on-site absolute LH₂ flow measurement error can be in the order of 2 % to 3 %.

The CMF analytical temperature correction models introduce an (uncorrected) error with concomitant uncertainty. This error was meticulously evaluated for typical tube designs in Chapter 4. The best agreement (within ± 0.2 % for the curved tubes) between the analytical model and the numerical FE model is achieved by the analytical correction model that considers the known temperature dependence of the tube elastic properties as well as the dimensional changes due to thermal strain [31]. This indicates that the uncertainty contribution from the analytical temperature correction model can be sufficiently small (i.e., uncertainty < 0.5 % with respect to flow rate) for certain CMF tube designs. The calibration errors of Chapter 3 included the automatic temperature correction feature. Figure 3-1 shows that the error of the CMF on LNG falls within $\pm 0.5\%$ with an approximate 95% coverage probability (for flow rates greater than 0.8 kg/s).

7.2 Recommendations to improve LH₂ flow measurement uncertainty

1. Proving by a dedicated flow standard with direct traceability to SI-units is recommended to corroborate the estimated measurement uncertainty from transferability of water and LNG calibrations to LH₂ conditions. [For further details please refer to Chapter 3].
2. More accurate measurements of the Coriolis tubes' Young's modulus (and, potentially, a more accurate approximation of the Young's modulus at temperatures below -233 °C) are recommended to reduce the uncertainty of the stiffness temperature correction method as it applies to Coriolis mass flow meters (CMF). This could potentially result in a reduction of the the difference between the measurement value obtained using the density correction method and that obtained using the aforementioned method as applicable to CMFs. The uncertainty of the Young's modulus should be evaluated in accordance with the GUM 'Evaluation of measurement data - Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement' [22]. [For further details please refer to Chapter 3].
3. When calibrating LH₂ flow meters through a transfer standard, it is recommended that a mass flow rate-based transfer standard (e.g., Coriolis mass flow meter) should be utilized for applications where the total LH₂ mass is of interest, or volume-based standard (e.g., turbine flow meter) should be employed for applications where the total LH₂ volume is of interest.
4. In the event that recommendation 3 cannot be followed, it is essential to carefully assess and account for the uncertainty associated with on-site LH₂ density estimation in the evaluation of LH₂ flow meter calibration uncertainty. The primary uncertainty source identified in Chapter 3 was the on-site density estimation required to convert the volume flow measurements into mass flow measurements. [For further details please refer to Chapter 3].
5. It is recommended to assess the accuracy of LH₂ temperature measurement systems. The accuracy of temperature measurements affects several quantities that are relevant to the accuracy of LH₂ flow measurement. This has a direct effect on the computation of LH₂ density when it is calculated through an equation of state (EOS). This also affects the accuracy of analytical temperature correction models, as applicable to CMFs [7], [25]. It is additionally relevant to estimate the thermal expansion (contraction) of flow meter materials and the potential resulting strain. It is observed that the accuracy of temperature measurement systems can be evaluated under LNG flow conditions as a proxy, with a direct link to the SI-units, in the LNG facility referenced in Chapter 3. [For further details please refer to Chapter 3 and Chapter 4].
6. In order to convert the volume flow measurements into mass flow measurements, it is necessary to perform on-site density estimation. It is probable that the calibration uncertainty will be lower when comparing meters that measure mass (or volume) flow rate. The results indicate the need for the implementation of reliable and accurate temperature measurements (which will allow for the generation of an accurate density estimate) so that volume-based (turbine, ultrasonic) and mass-based (Coriolis) quantity measurements in LH₂ custody transfer processes can be compared with smaller uncertainties.
7. It is advised that the temperature range in the empirical determination of the Poisson's ratio is extended, as applicable to Coriolis mass flow meters in the analytical model C of Chapter 4, in order to further reduce this uncertainty source. [For further details please refer to Chapter 4].
8. Further studies are recommended into the uncertainty of analytical temperature correction models as they apply to CMFs, given the potential scenario of continued scarcity of directly SI-traceable LH₂ flow calibration facilities. It is observed that the cryogenic LDV presented in Chapter 6 can be used either as a primary standard or as a secondary standard during LH₂ flow measurements in industrial process conditions (1000 kg/h to 5000 kg/h and pressures up to 10 bar(a); DN25 to DN 50). Furthermore, the effectiveness of analytical temperature correction models can be studied in the LNG facility referenced in Chapter 3, with a direct link to the SI-units. [For further details please refer to Chapters 3, 4, and 6].

SI-traceable measurement uncertainty of liquefied hydrogen flow

7.3 Guidance on Coriolis meter deviations when using the vaporisation method

Due to the limited number of studied cases a general statement on Guidance on CMF deviations when using the vaporisation method is not possible. Nevertheless, the following information should be taken into account when using CFMs:

1. The stability of the meter's zero point represents a significant challenge. Despite efforts to ensure reproducibility, achieving a consistent zero point under stable conditions proved unattainable. Consequently, the approach of recording the zero point before and after each measurement was favoured, although this introduced further limitations concerning the vaporization test rig.
2. The utilised Coriolis meter exhibited a deviation between the initial calibration with water and the subsequent calibration with dry gas. This discrepancy is primarily a consequence of the oversizing of the meter for the intended flow range. However, the selection of a larger meter was driven by the concern that the pressure loss at lower flow rates might not adequately compensate for the low inlet pressure. It is important to note that the selected meter size was not optimal for the intended experiments.
3. With regards to the measurements conducted with LHe, further investigations are required to clarify the reasons why the liquid phase of helium was not reached at the MUT. As previously stated, it is hypothesized that the wiring or the generated heat from the operation of the oversized Coriolis meter are the probable causes.

The vaporisation method results have the potential to use the CMF in the liquid phase. Yet the reached uncertainty was below 2 %. Taking into account the optimisation potential of the test facility lower uncertainties might be possible.

References

- [1] European Commission, “Communication from the commission to the european parliament, the european council, the council, the european economic and social committee and the committee of the regions, “the european green deal”,” 2019. [Online].
- [2] European Commission, “Communication from the commission to the european, “a hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral europe”,” 2020. [Online].
- [3] ISO, “ISO/IEC 17025:2017, General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories,” 2017. [Online].
- [4] de Jonge, T.; Patten, T.; Rivetti, A.; Serio, L. , “Development of a mass flowmeter based on the Coriolis acceleration for liquid, supercritical and superfluid helium,” in *19th International Cryogenic Engineering Conference*, 2002.
- [5] Schakel, M., “Liquid nitrogen calibrations of industry-standard LNG flow meters used in LNG custody transfer,” VSL - National Metrology Institute, 2019.
- [6] Kenbar, A.; Schakel, M., “Influence of flow disturbances on the performance of industry-standard LNG flow meters,” *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, vol. 77, p. 101871. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flowmeasinst.2020.101871>, 2020.
- [7] F. Gugole, D. Standiford, J. Kutin and O. Bükler, “Uncertainty in U-shape Coriolis mass flow meter for liquid hydrogen measurements,” Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows project report, 2022.
- [8] Raszillier, H.; Durst, F., “Coriolis-effect in mass flow metering. Archive of Applied Mechanics,” vol. 61, pp. 192–214, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00788053>, 1991.
- [9] Costa, F.O., Pope, J.G., Gillis, K.A., “Modeling temperature effects on a Coriolis mass flowmeter,” *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, vol. 76, pp. 101811, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flowmeasinst.2020.101811>, 2020.
- [10] Wu, T. Y.; Kenbar, A.; Pruysen, A., “LNG mass flowrate measurement using Coriolis flowmeters: Analysis of the measurement uncertainties,” *Measurement*, vol. 177, pp. 109258, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2021.109258>, 2021.
- [11] Wu, T. Y.; Kenbar, A., “LNG mass flow measurement uncertainty reduction using calculated Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio for Coriolis flowmeters,” *Measurement*, vol. 188, pp. 110413, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2021.110413>, 2022.
- [12] A. T. Patten and R. B. Garnett, “Method of compensating for mass flow using known density”. Patent US 11,486,752 B2, 2022.
- [13] BIPM; IEC; IFCC; ILAC; ISO; IUPAC; IUPAP; and OIML, “Supplement 1 to the guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurements - propagation of distributions using a Monte Carlo method,” BIPM, 2008.

- [14] Christie, R.; Hartwig, J. , “Thermal acoustic oscillation: causes, detection, analysis, and prevention,” in *Thermal & Fluids analysis workshop*, 2014.
- [15] Emerson, M.M., “Micro motion elite coriolis flow and density meters. Product data sheet,” 2023. [Online].
- [16] Ledbetter, H. M. , “Stainless-steel elastic constants at low temperatures,” . *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 52, pp. 1587–1589, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.329644>, 1981.
- [17] Kuhny, D., “Compensating for the effects of high pressure on the measurement accuracy of coriolis flowmeters,” *Micro Motion*, 2011.
- [18] Mills, C., “Calibrating and operating Coriolis flow meters with respect to process effects,” *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, vol. 71, pp. 101649, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flowmeasinst.2019.101649>, 2020.
- [19] NIST, “Material Properties: 316 Stainless,” 2023. [Online]. Available: https://trc.nist.gov/cryogenics/materials/316Stainless/316Stainless_rev.htm. [Accessed 2023 11 2023].
- [20] Span, R.; Beckmüller, R.; Hielscher, S.; Jäger, A.; Mickoleit, E.; Neumann, T.; Pohl, S.; Semrau, B.; Thol, M., *TREND. Thermodynamic reference and engineering data 5.0*, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, 2020.
- [21] Leachman, J. W.; Jacobsen, R. T.; Penoncello, S. G.; Lemmon, E. W., “Fundamental Equations of State for Parahydrogen, Normal Hydrogen, and Orthohydrogen,” *Journal of Physical and Chemical Reference Data*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 721–748, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3160306>, 2009.
- [22] BIPM; IEC; IFCC; ILAC; ISO; IUPAC; IUPAP; and OIML, “Evaluation of measurement data — Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement, JCGM 100:2008, GUM:1995 with minor corrections,” BIPM, 2008.
- [23] Ledbetter, H. M., “Sound velocities and elastic constants of steels 304, 310, and 316,” *Metal Science*, vol. 14, no. 12, pp. 595–596, <https://doi.org/10.1179/030634580790426166>, 1980.
- [24] Ledbetter, H. M.; Frederick, N. V.; Austin, M. W., “Elastic-constant variability in stainless-steel 304,” *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 305–309, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.327371>, 1980.
- [25] Standiford, D., “Calibration is the key,” *LNG Industry*, August 2021.
- [26] Saecker, D., “Process thermometer assembly optimized for usage in cryogenic and liquefied gases,” in *European Flow Measurement Workshop 2023 - special edition*, 2023.
- [27] van der Beek, M.; Lucas, P.; Kerkhof, O.; Mirzaei, M.; Blom, G., “Results of the evaluation and preliminary validation of a primary LNG mass flow standard,” *Metrologia*, vol. 51, no. 5, pp. 539, [10.1088/0026-1394/51/5/539](https://doi.org/10.1088/0026-1394/51/5/539), 2014.

- [28] Kunz, O.; Wagner, W., "The GERG-2008 wide-range equation of state for natural gases and other mixtures: An expansion of GERG-2004," *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data*, vol. 57 , no. 11, pp. 3032–3091, <https://doi.org/10.1021/je300655b>, 2012.
- [29] ISO, "Natural gas - Calculation of thermodynamic properties - Part 2: Single-phase properties (gas, liquid, and dense fluid) for extended ranges of applications," 2015. [Online].
- [30] Maury, R.; Strzelecki, A.; Auclercq, C.; Lehot, Y.; Loubat, S.; Chevalier, J.; Ben Rayana, f.; Olsen, Å A F.; Chupin, G., "Cryogenic flow rate measurement with a laser Doppler velocimetry standard. Measurement Science and Technology," *Measurement Science and Technology*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 034009, 10.1088/1361-6501/aa9dd1, 2018.
- [31] F. Gugole, D. Standiford, J. Kutin, O. Bükler and M. Schakel, "Uncertainty in U-tube Coriolis mass flow meters for liquid hydrogen measurements," in *CIM*, Lyon, 2023.
- [32] M. Schakel, F. Gugole, D. Standiford, J. Kutin, G. Bobovnik, N. Mole, R. Maury, D. Schumann, R. Kramer, C. Guenz, H.-B. Boeckler and O. Bueker, "Establish traceability for liquefied hydrogen flow measurements," in *Flomeko*, Chongqing, 2022.
- [33] Kutin, J.; Bobovnik, G.; Mole, N.; Schakel, M.D.; Bükler, O., "Measurement corrections for temperature effects in Coriolis mass flow meters for cryogenic, liquid hydrogen (LH2) applications," *Measurement*, p. Submitted January 2024, 2024.
- [34] Gugole, F.; Schakel, M.D.; Brugman, M.; Druzhkov, A., "Assessment of alternative fluid calibration to estimate traceable liquefied hydrogen flow measurement uncertainty," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, p. Submitted April 2024, 2024.